

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MAGAI****FIRST NAME: DANIEL AJAK****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Gulma**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US*The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:*The author did use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did use GrammarlyThe author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2013 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE DSDD-401D

1. The American English variant has grown in potential influence and seem to be taking the world at large as advanced by key factors since world two. What are these factors?
- The influence of American during the cold war and liberal ideologies toward the new world order.
 - The mass media, technology, publishing industry, American sociopolitical and economic position, and higher education magnitude.¹**
 - The America's control on world political ideologies.
 - It is through American wealth and funding that the world is adjusting to American English.

¹ Laurent Cleenerwerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 25.

2. Research is one of the key and complex activities in the academic world and any other area. In accordance with Turabian 2018, provide a correct definition of research and its important.

- Research is explained as the basis for establishing truth and convincing the audience to follow that truth.
- Research is a process of analyzing different projects to present a suitable and solution-based program for the activities.
- Research is the conduct of surveys and adventuring tour to discover new places and inform the world of their existence.
- Research is as a process of systematic inquiry to offer an explanation to research questions, share the results and conclusions to allow the conversation continuity, and provide possible solutions.²**

3. With the understanding of research in accordance with Turabian 2008, and Bloomberg and Volpe 2019, which of the following statements provides a comprehensive description of the introduction to the research?

- The introduction defines what is to be studied and its worth, explaining and justifying the research and drawing readers into the nature and problem being addressed as well as the conceptual frame in use.³**

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th Edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing | Includes Bibliographical References and Index. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 19–22.

³ Ibid., 70, 110–14; Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*, Fourth Edition (Los Angeles: California: SAGE Publication, Inc., 2019), 205, 306–30.

- The introduction chapter detailed the significance of the study and provide the readers with the results of the research conducted.
 - The introduction chapter explains the literature of the research and approaches used to analyze the results and provide the explanation of key concepts of the research.
 - Being always the first chapter of the study, the introduction provides the structural order of the research, explains the data collection methods to be used including the sampling techniques as the research is concerned.
4. The differences and similarities of punctuations in British and American English variants are clear and must be adhered to in research. In reference to the European Commission 2016, and Cleenerwerck and Gulma 2021, Explain how quotation marks are applied in British English.
- The British English requires the use of curly and single quotation marks in direct speech and verbatim quotes, double quote is used within these and indented quote do not take quotation marks.⁴**
 - The British English used generally double quotation marks with no specific preferences while the indented quotes take the appropriate single quotes at the opening and closing.
 - The British English has no specific differences in using the quotations marks, hence any quote style can be use same as in American English variant.

⁴ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, ed. Daniel Alexander et al., Eighth Edition (European Commission, 2016), 14, https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/styleguide_english_dgt_en.pdf; Cleenerwerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 23, 31–32.

- The use of quotation marks has no definite restriction in British English, both the curly, straight quotes either double or single can be used at will.
5. In qualitative research, the Theoretical/Conceptual framework is presented as a very important section one must adequately develop. In reference to Bloomberg and Volpe 2019, provide its best description and importance?
- The theoretical/conceptual framework is always the basis of the research design and supports the researcher to construct the research questions and develop an introduction to the research.
- A conceptual or theoretical framework is the methodology of the research that provides a way to analyze the research results in relation to the design and approaches used.
- A theoretical framework is the application of a theory to offer an explanation of an event or shed some light on a particular phenomenon or research problem whereas a conceptual framework uses concepts to provides a broader understanding of a phenomenon of interest or of a research problem forming the bases for the development of the study and analysis of the findings.⁵**
- A theoretical or conceptual framework provides the basis for the analysis of findings and results but does not offer any significant guidance to the research problem or research focus. It is that important and it's absent in qualitative research can be okay.

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*, 206–7, 267–68, 395–408.

6. In academic writing and research, plagiarism is a crime. With an example, explains plagiarism in reference to Turabian 2018, and Cleenerwerck and Gulma 2021.

Plagiarism is an academic theft of ideas or methods without acknowledgment, for instant quotes, concepts, use of words or paraphrasing ideas from a source but failing to cite them correctly.⁶

Plagiarism is the process of taking the resources and citing the right sources but failing to mention your own contribution toward their writing.

Plagiarism is the collection of information from different writers, using it exactly as they are, and indicating the origin of such texts, including the pages and authors.

Plagiarism is the tool for assessing and selecting the right sources and information to inform the research or essay.

7. The European Union legislation has evolved over decades if not centuries through changes. Notably, the Treaty of Lisbon made critical changes, what are they?

The renaming of the European Community to European Union and establishing a position for the High Representative for the European Parliament.

The important changes include creating the European Council and establishing the European Parliament as one of the most powerful parliaments in the union.

The Treaty introduced key additions to the EU treaty and the treaty Establishing the European Community but never changed, rename or amend the treaties.

⁶ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 80–82, 139–41; Cleenerwerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 33–39.

- The Treaty of Lisbon amended the treaty on European Union and the Treaty Establishing the European Community, renaming the latter and introducing changes including European Community being absorbed into the European Union, European Council made an independent institution with a President, among other key changes.⁷**

8. Note-taking is one of the crucial aspects of literature review and source searching in the research. In reference to Turabian 2008, what key information should be included in the note?

- Taking notes requires information such as the source (author-date), the quote itself, or a summary of the note with a specific page number and title of the source as well as understanding the context, comment may be added.⁸**
- It quires that the researcher put down his own summary of the quote and provide the paraphrasing without indicating the source as long it is summarized.
- Notetaking is not an easy task, it quires the information of the author only, and the specificities such as the quotes and page number are not required.
- Note-taking requires the understanding of the context of the passage read as this will help the writer understand better and recording of the author's name and title of the book only, a page number is not required.

⁷ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 75.

⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 48–53.

9. Going by the general understanding of in-text citation in accordance to Turabian (2008), and Cleenerwerck and Gulma (2021), the best way to insert such citations is?

- Author-date style, inserted in parentheses indicating the author's last name, year of publishing, and the page number e.g. (Aisha 2020, 20).⁹**
- Author-date style, inserted mostly as part of the text indicating the first and last names of the author and year of publication only.
- A shorten citation where the name of the author is mentioned, the name of the book and the year of publication with no specific page or location.
- A citation that takes in both the year and date of publication but omitting the author name or any other information.

10. In accordance to Cleenerwerck and Gulma (2021), and Turabian (2008), what is the best way to insert a long or block quote citation in the work?

- The long quote is inserted as a block, indented with single space before and after without quotation mark unless internal quotation, then the source.¹⁰**
- The block quotation is always place within the parentheses and as a standalone passage then the source.
- Long passage quoted is always placed alone but not indented.
- The block quotation or indented quotation can be only 3 lines or less than that and note more than 4 lines.

⁹ Turabian, 141,228-300; Cleenerwerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 35.

¹⁰ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 372–73; Cleenerwerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 35–36.

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